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RADIATION AND CHEMICAL SAFETY PROBLEMS

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DOSE RATE DEPENDENCE OF THERMOLUMINESCENCE SIGNAL OF NATURAL QUARTZ

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Thermoluminescence (TL) is a well established method to determine the energy dose absorbed by natural minerals, such as quartz and feldspar. A key aspect in the accuracy of luminescence dating is the reproducibility of natural processes in the laboratory. But dose rates applied in the laboratory differ by several orders of magnitude from the dose rate in nature. The effect of different dose rates on TL signals of quartz were investigated in different studies: McKeever et al. (2002) reported a considerable decrease of TL response in powdered samples of Brazilian crystalline quartz when irradiated with a ^{60}Co source at dose rates ranging from 1.4 mGy s^{-1} to 3.3 Gy s^{-1} . Valladas and Ferrera (1980) investigated rock crystal TL by applying different filters: peak at $320 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ decreases by 40% when dose rate increases, while peak at $360 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increases by 60% but peak at $370 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ presents a small increase.

We experimentally observed that depicts the TL glow curves of both natural and preheated quartz samples at two different dose rates. TL intensity of both natural and preheated sand samples decreases by increasing of dose rate. Some basic observations can be summarized as follows:

- The higher dose rates the smaller the signal intensity,
- Both natural and preheated samples show the same dose rate response behavior.